

AWARENESS AND UTILIZATION OF ELECTRONIC JOURNALS BY THE MEMBERS OF FACULTY AND RESEARCH SCHOLARS OF MADURAI KAMARAJ UNIVERSITY, MADURAI

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Abstract:

This paper ascertains the awareness and utilization of electronic journals by the members of faculty and research scholars of Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai. It is found that 85.5% respondents access Open source journals, 78.6% respondents access E-Journals daily while 91% of the respondents use e- journals for writing journal articles. 83.4% respondents access E- Journals in Library and 57.2% respondents cite that difficulty of accessing electronic journals is trouble in finding relevant information from E-journals. 67.6% of the respondents' opinion about usefulness of E-Journals is great extent. It is inferred from the Chi-square analysis that there is no association between the respondents' gender and their opinion about the level of satisfaction of the E -journals.

Key Words: E -Journals, UGC-INFONET Journals, Open Access Journals & Internet

Introduction:

Journals in a library play vital role in distributing nascent facts and primary information to users. They publish articles and papers on recent research and development, particularly in the ever changing fields of management, science, and technology. Advent of electronic journals (e-journals) during recent years has given librarians a powerful new resource to support learning and research. Lot of journals, in all fields, both printed as well as electronic, are currently available electronically via web. Electronic journals in all subjects are now widely available and the pricing and licensing models are now becoming established. Electronic journals can take the form of electronic versions of printed journals, usually available in conjunction with a subscription to a printed title, or electronic only publications. Some are freely available, but often titles require subscription as viewed. The goal of e - journal is to provide desktop access freely available electronic version of journals. The users are required to visit the sites for using and can access the full text of articles.

Objectives of the Study:

The main objectives of the present study are as follows.

- ✓ To analyse the awareness and utilization of E-journals by the faculty members and research scholars of Madurai Kamaraj University.
- ✓ To study the frequency of access E-journals.
- ✓ To find out the purpose of using E-journals.
- ✓ To know the location of accessing E-journals.
- ✓ To know the opinion about the difficulty of accessing electronic journals.
- ✓ To study the opinion about extent of usefulness of E-Journals.
- ✓ To study the level of satisfaction of the respondents regarding the use of E-journals.

Methodology:

The present study is a survey method using a questionnaire. A total number of 175 Questionnaires were randomly distributed to the members of faculty and research scholars of Madurai Kamaraj University, Tamilnadu, India. Out of 175 questionnaires,

145 filled questionnaires were received back by the researchers. Hence selected 145 questionnaires were used for data analysis and interpretation. Secondary data were collected from journals, books and theses. Primary data have been collected on August 2016.

Scope of the Study:

The title of research is "Awareness and utilization of electronic journals by the members of faculty and research scholars of Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai". The target group of this study includes members of faculty and research scholars of Madurai Kamaraj University. Their activities regarding the awareness and utilization of E-journals have been analysed. The geographical area of this study is confined only to Madurai city.

Review of Literature:

Borrego (2007)¹ presented the results of a survey on the use of electronic journals by the academic staff of the universities belonging to the Consortium of Academic Libraries of Catalonia (CBUC). The results showed that a high proportion of teaching and research staff are aware of the collection of electronic journals and that there is an increasing preference for the electronic to the detriment of the printed format. The collection of electronic journals was highly valued and most users expect to increase their use of them during the next few years. The results also confirmed the importance of user's discipline and age as explanatory factors of the use of electronic journals. The preference for the electronic format was higher among academic staff in Biomedicine, Engineering and Exact and Natural Sciences.

Davis and Solla (2003)² analysed the e-journals download in American Chemical Society electronic journal downloads at Cornell University (Ithaca, New York) by individual IP (Internet Protocol) addresses. It highlights include usage statistics to evaluate library journal subscriptions.

De Groote, et al., (2005)³ studied online journals impact on the citation patterns of medical faculty at the University of Illinois at Chicago (UIC). That study looked at whether researchers were more likely to limit the resources they consulted and cited to those journals available online rather than those only in print. Searches by author affiliation were performed in the Web of Science to find all articles written by faculty members. The number of journals cited per year continued to increase from 1993 to 2002. It was possible that electronic access to information (Online databases) had a positive impact on the number of articles faculty would cite.

Dhingra and Mahajan, (2007)⁴ presented the results of over the last few years there has been a rapid rise in the electronic journals and this electronic delivery of journals has resulted this study. Users of the E-journals in the A.C. Joshi Library, Punjab University, Chandigarh were studied in this survey. Study highlights the level of the use of the available electronic journals. Experiences of faculty and students about various issues relating to electronic journals are highlighted.

Dilek-Kayaoglu (2008)⁵ conducted a study to examine the use of electronic journals by faculty at Istanbul University, Turkey. Major findings of the study are: (i) 89% of the respondents stated that one of the benefits of e-journals was that there was no need to visit the library (ii) 67.5% of the respondents stated that they used e-journals for research, 49.2% used them for keeping him/herself updated on the subject field, 28.5% for browsing core journals, and 16.9% for teaching enables researchers to move more easily from one level to another and thus to take advantage of the more appropriate opportunities.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Distribution of respondents by Gender

S.No	Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Male	79	54.5
2	Female	66	45.5
Total		145	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents by Gender. In this study, 79 (54.5%) respondents are male whereas 66 (45.5%) respondents are female. Hence more than half of the respondents belong to the category of male.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents by Status

S.No	Status	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Faculty members	45	31
2	Research Scholars	100	69
Total		145	100

Source: Primary Data

It could be observed from table 2 that 45 (31%) respondents belong to faculty members whereas 100 (69%) respondents research scholars. Hence a majority of the respondents belong to the category of research scholars.

Table 3: Distribution of respondents by Domicile Sector

S.No	Domicile Sector	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Rural	57	39.3
2.	Urban	88	60.7
Total		145	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 3 indicates that a majority of 88 (60.7%) respondents belong to urban areas while rest of the 57 (39.3%) respondents rural areas. That is, most of the respondents belong to urban areas.

Table 4: Preference of using E-journals

S.No	Types of journals	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Open source journals	124	85.5
2.	UGC-Infonet journals	85	58.6
3.	Subscribed journals	93	64.1
Total N=145			

Source: Primary Data

Multiple Responses

It is understood from the table 4 that among the overall respondents, a majority of 85.5% of the respondents access Open source journals and it is followed by 64.1% subscribed journals while 58.6% UGC- Infonet journals.

Table 5: Frequency of accessing E-Journals

S.No.	Frequency	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Daily	114	78.6
2	Once in a week	15	10.3
3	Twice in a week	9	6.2
4	Occasionally	7	4.8
Total		145	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 5 reveals that a majority of 114(78.6%) respondents access E-Journals daily and it is followed by, 15 (10.3%) respondents once in a week, 9(6.2%) respondents twice in a week while 7(4.8%) respondents occasionally. Hence more than three fourths of the respondents access E-journals daily.

Figure 1: Frequency of accessing E-Journals

Table 6: Purpose of using E- Journals

S.No	Propose	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	For writing journal articles	132	91
2	For projects	83	57.2
3	For preparing class notes	97	66.9
4	For Seminar	78	53.8
5	For Research work	114	78.6
6.	Others	13	9
Total N =145			

Source: Primary Data

Multiple Responses

It is focused from the table 6 that majority of 91% respondents are using e-journals for writing journal articles, and it is followed by 78.6% for Research work, 66.9% for preparing class notes, 57.2% for projects whereas 53.8% for seminar. Besides cited above, there are some other purposes also (9%). Therefore majority of the respondents are using e – journals for writing journal articles.

Table 7: Location of accessing E- Journals

S.No	Location	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Net Café	32	22.1
2.	Home	43	29.7
3.	Department	94	64.8
4.	Library	121	83.4
5.	Hostel	17	11.7
Total N =145			

Source: Primary data

Multiple Responses

Table 7 presents the location of accessing E- Journals by the respondents. In this study, a majority of 83.4% respondents access E- Journals in Library and it is followed

by 64.8% respondents access E- Journals in their Departments, 29.7% Home, 22.7% net cafe and 11.7% access in Hostel.

Table 8: Opinion about the difficulty of accessing electronic journals

S.No	Difficulty	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Lack of Infrastructure	39	26.9
2.	Trouble in finding relevant information	83	57.2
3.	Lack of Training	57	39.3
4.	Others	53	36.6
Total N =145			

Source: Primary data

Multiple Responses

It could be observed from table 8 that majority of 57.2% respondents cite that difficulty of accessing electronic journals is trouble in finding relevant information. This is followed by, 39.3% of them cite that lack of training, 36.6% of them other hindrances while 26.9% of them lack of infrastructure. Hence more than half of the respondents cite that difficulty of accessing electronic journals is trouble in finding relevant information.

Table 9: Opinion about extent of usefulness of E-Journals

S.No	Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Great extent	98	67.6
2.	Small extent	36	24.8
3.	Not at all	11	7.6
Total		145	100

Source: Primary Data

It is understood from table 9 that majority of 98(67.6%) respondents' opinion about usefulness of E-Journals is great extent and it is followed by 36(24.8%) respondents' opinion is small extent whereas 11(7.6%) not at all. It is concluded that majority of the respondents' opinion of usefulness of E-Journals is great extent.

Table 10: Chi- square analysis of opinion about the level of satisfaction of the E-journals by status-wise respondents

S.No	Status	Opinion (%)					Total
		Excellent	Very Good	Good	Poor	No Comments	
1.	Research Scholars	58 (58)	24 (24)	6 (6)	5 (5)	7 (7)	100
2.	Faculty members	21 (46.7)	8 (17.8)	5 (11.1)	5 (11.1)	6 (13.3)	45
Total		79	32	11	10	13	145

Source: Primary data Chi- square value: 5.6 df = 4

Data presented in table 10 reveals the Chi- square analysis of opinion about the level of satisfaction of the E-journals by status-wise respondents. A majority of 58 (58%) research scholars' opinion about the level of satisfaction of the E-journals is excellent and it is followed by 24(24%) of them opine that it is very good, 7 (7%) respondents have not expressed any comments,6 (6%) of them good and 5(5%) of them poor respectively. Among the faculty members, a majority (46.7%) of them opine that the level of satisfaction of the E-journals is excellent and it is followed by 17.8% of them very good, 11.1% good and poor while 13.3% have not expressed any comments. Therefore 54.5% of the male and female respondents' opinion about the level of satisfaction of the E-journals is excellent.

Testing of Hypothesis:

Ho: Null Hypothesis:

There is no association between the respondents' gender and their opinion about the level of satisfaction of the E –journals.

Chi-Square Summary Result:

Chi-Square calculated Value	Degrees of Freedom	Chi-Square Table Value @ 5%
5.6	4	9.488

The table value of χ^2 for 4 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance is 9.488. The calculated value of χ^2 is lower than this table value and hence the Null hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is no association between the respondents' gender and their opinion about the level of satisfaction of the E –journals.

Major Findings:

- ✓ 54.5% of the respondents belong to the category of male.
- ✓ 69% of the respondents belong to the category of research scholars.
- ✓ 60.7% respondents belong to urban areas.
- ✓ 85.5% of respondents access Open source journals.
- ✓ 78.6% of the respondents access e- journals daily.
- ✓ 91% of the respondents are using e – journals for writing journal articles.
- ✓ 83.4% respondents access E- Journals through Library.
- ✓ 57.2% respondents cite that hindrance of accessing electronic journals is difficulty in finding relevant information.
- ✓ 67.6% the respondents' opinion of usefulness of E-Journals is great extent.
- ✓ There is no association between the respondents' gender and their opinion about the level of satisfaction of the E –journals.

Suggestions:

- ✓ It is suggested that the library authority should conduct orientation programme periodically regarding the use of E-journals to attract all the research scholars and members of faculty to use the university library.
- ✓ It is suggested that the university authorities should allocate more funds for installation of more computers with internet connection in libraries.
- ✓ It is suggested that the library authorities should subscribe more number of E-journals both national and international level for fulfill the need of the researchers.

Conclusion:

E-journals are part of a cluster of innovations and technologies that can be leveraged to create value for scholars. This study was aimed to make an analytical study on the use of electronic Journal provided to faculty members and research scholars in the Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai. ICT is like a sun around which e-resources, e-services and e-users are revolving. So that each and every library or information centre, are to be equipped, with modern electronic equipments. This definitely helps the library professionals to reach the user community and satisfy their information requirements to a greater extent. The study shows that users who participated in this survey are almost aware of e-journals. Most of the faculty members and research scholars use e-journals for their writing journal articles and research work. Hence it is necessary that the library authorities should teach their users about various search strategies to access the E-journals effectively.

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